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Sestrin activation during nutrient deprivation in human cells.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Autophagy connects nutrient sensing to changes in cellular uptake and phospholipase-independent activity at the membrane. We hypothesized that links mTOR and amino acid sensing are intrinsically linked to the autophagy system. We demonstrate here that Sestrin 2 is activated during nutrient restriction and that Sestrin activation is a central component of nutrient deprivation in human cells.